

ISic3698

I.Sicily inscription 3698

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary (?)

Material

limestone

Object

column

(?)

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Megara Hyblaea

Place of origin (modern)

Megara Iblea

Provenance

found in 1965, east of the Hellenistic walls

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Megara Hyblaea, Antiquarium di Megara
Hyblaia

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI330087

1. ΞΕΝ [— — — —]

2. Ο,ΑΚ Λ [— — —]

3. [—]Η. [— — —]

4. [— — — — —]

5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

PHI 330087

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 26.1096

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1975. Koiné alfabetica fra Siracusa, Megara Iblea e Selinunte?. *Kokalos*. 21: 121-153. At 152-153 no.19 tav.34.2

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